

Acid Catalysed Bromination of *p*-Phenylacetophenone

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The bromination of *p*-phenylacetophenone has been found to be acid catalysed, dependent on the concentration of ketone and independent of the concentration of bromine. Reaction proceeds both via neutral and conjugate acid species. Experimental rates have been confirmed by those determined from ionic strength data. Detailed kinetic study using concepts as solvent effect, solvent isotope effect, Arrhenius parameters indicate the bimolecular nucleophilic attack of water on conjugate acid species.

IN the acid catalysed iodination of acetophenone derivatives proton removal is the rate determining step and the reaction is much more proportional to concentration of H^+ ions than to H_0 function¹. The bromination of *p*-nitro, *p*-chloro, *p*-bromoacetophenones have been found to be acid catalysed and subject to negative salt effect.^{2a,b} No work appears to have been done on acid catalysed bromination of *p*-phenylacetophenone in quantitative salt solutions ; hence the acid catalysed bromination of *p*-phenylacetophenone has been studied and results are discussed in this paper.

Experimental

All chemicals used during present investigation were of A. R. grade.

p-phenylacetophenone was prepared from diphenyl, acetic anhydride and anhydrous aluminium chloride and was purified several times by recrystallization.³

Kinetic Studies

The rates of bromination of *p*-phenylacetophenone were studied in 50:50 alcohol water mixtures at 30° with ketone concentration at 0.03M. Aliquots were taken out at intervals, potassium iodide was added and iodine liberated was titrated with standard hypo. Pseudo first order rate coefficients were calculated. Rates of bromination have been measured as rates of enolization⁴.

HCl-KCl and HCl potassium hydrogenphthalate buffers were used as given by Stene⁵.

Deuterium oxide of isotopic purity >99.4% was procured from B.A.R.C., Trombay.

Results and Discussion

The bromination of *p*-phenylacetophenone has been studied in sulphuric and perchloric acids and in buffers in the range pH 1.2 to 3.97. The results are summarized in Table 1 and pH-log rate profile has been shown in Figure 1.

H_2SO_4 (M)	$10k \text{ Sec}^{-1}$	$HClO_4$ (M)	$10k \text{ Sec}^{-1}$ (Experimental)	$10k \text{ Sec}^{-1}$ (Calculated)
0.5	17.00	0.5	24.17	25.78
0.8	18.70	0.8	25.82	27.64
1.0	20.09	1.0	27.29	29.12
	12.46			
1.5	35.39	2.0	29.57	39.66
2.0	40.85	2.5	35.29	47.41
3.0	65.95	3.0	56.59	57.60
3.5	81.20			
4.0	131.90			

$\times D_2O$
 $E = 13.72 \text{ k Cal./mole}, A = 1.566 \times 10^8 \text{ Sec}^{-1}, \Delta S^\ddagger = -28.21 \text{ e.u.}$

Figure 1. pH-log rate profile for Bromination of *p*-Phenylacetophenone at 30°.

Rates for bromination increase linearly with increase in acid concentration and plots of log rates against H_0 shows the inapplicability of H_0 function, which indicates that reaction involves a nucleophilic attack of water molecule on conjugate acid species.⁴

Figure 2. Bromination of *p*-Phenylacetophenone at constant ionic strength at 30°.

Ionic strength effect was studied in order to know the cause of increase of rates^{6,7}. The ionic strength was kept constant with perchloric acid and sodium perchlorate. Rate constants were plotted against acid concentration at each ionic strength (Figure 2). The following conclusions can be drawn from ionic strength data.

(a) Rates of bromination decrease with increase in acid concentration at each ionic strength.

(b) Slopes of lines decrease with increase in ionic strength; hence negative salt effect is indicated.

(c) The lines do not pass through origin and have different intercepts on rate axis, which indicates that reaction also proceeds via neutral species.

The total rate of reaction can be represented by equation^{8,6b}.

$$K_e = K H_0 \exp b H^+ \mu + K N_0 \exp b N \mu$$

where K_e , $K H_0$, $b, K N_0$ and μ are the overall rates, specific acid catalysed rate, a constant specific neutral rate and ionic strength respectively. The sum of acid catalysed and neutral rates using above equation fairly agree well with experimental rates (Table 1). Solvent deuterium oxide effect shows a decrease in rate ($K D_2O / K H_2O < 1$) indicates that reaction involves a slow proton transfer as in the brominations of *p*-nitro, *p*-bromoacetophenone^{2b}. A few kinetic runs carried out in a series of ethanol water mixtures decreased the rates and a plot of $\log k/k_0$ against ionising power of medium (Y) gave slope less than unity, also shows the bimolecular nucleophilic attack of water on conjugate acid species¹⁰. The values of Arrhenius parameters are also consistent with bimolecular acid catalysed reaction¹¹. The reaction

consistent with results can thus be formulated as mentioned in the acid catalysed halogenations of other aromatic substituted ketones^{2,6}.

The final product of bromination has been isolated and identified as *p*-phenylphenacyl bromide.

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